

**MAIN FUNCTIONS OF EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT CENTERS IN DIFFERENT
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Annotation: This article covers essential facts about emergency management centers and their main tasks. On the other hands, components and basic phases of emergency management were highlighted.

Key words: *technological hazards, partnership, life cycle, private sector, Mitigation, Preparedness, Response, Recovery, financial assistance, Recovery activities.*

Emergency management was institutionalized in 1979 with the creation of the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA). Five Federal agencies that dealt with many types of emergencies consolidated to form FEMA. Since that time, many State and local organizations have changed the names of their organizations to include the words: emergency management. The name change indicates a change in orientation from specialized preparedness for single or narrowly defined categories of hazards toward an all-hazards approach that includes potential threats to life and property through environmental and technological hazards, and domestic and foreign attacks. This change reflects not a reduction in security, but an increased emphasis on making the nation's emergency management capability responsive to any major emergency[1]. The concept of emergency management consists of three interrelated components, as shown below:

1. All types of hazards: There are many common features of technological and natural disasters and attack, suggesting that many of the same management strategies can apply to all emergencies.

2. An emergency management partnership: Finding resources for disaster management requires a partnership among all levels of government (local, State, and Federal) and the private sector (business and industry, voluntary organizations, and the public). This approach also allows the disaster victims to contribute to emergency management solutions. Emergency managers and the animal-care community can collaborate in such a partnership.

3. An emergency life cycle: Disasters do not just appear one day — they exist throughout time and have a life cycle of occurrence. This cycle is matched by a series of management phases: establish strategies to mitigate hazards; prepare for and respond to emergencies; and recover from effects.

Many States require that local jurisdictions provide for the position of emergency program manager. At each level of government, laws define the responsibility and authority of emergency managers and management programs. If you know how emergency management works at the various governmental levels, you can coordinate your personal preparedness plans with official community plans. You may even become a part of your local or State emergency management program. Coordination of knowledge, resources and expertise between government officials and the private sector is a basic principle of emergency management. Since World War II emergency management has focused primarily on preparedness. Often this involved preparing for enemy attack. Community preparedness for all disasters requires identifying resources and expertise in advance, and planning how these can be used in a disaster. However, preparedness is only one phase of emergency management. Current thinking defines four phases of emergency management: mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery. There are entire courses on each of these phases. Below we can see main four phases of emergency management[2]:

- Mitigation. Preventing future emergencies or minimizing their effects- Includes any activities that prevent an emergency, reduce the chance of an emergency happening, or reduce the damaging effects of unavoidable emergencies. Buying flood and fire insurance for your home is a mitigation activity. Mitigation activities take place before and after emergencies.

- Preparedness. Preparing to handle an emergency. Includes plans or preparations made to save lives and to help response and rescue operations. Evacuation plans and stocking food and water are both examples of preparedness. Preparedness activities take place before an emergency occurs.

- Response. Responding safely to an emergency. Includes actions taken to save lives and prevent further property damage in an emergency situation. Response is putting

your preparedness plans into action. Seeking shelter from a tornado or turning off gas valves in an earthquake are both response activities. Response activities take place during an emergency.

- Recovery. Recovering from an emergency. Includes actions taken to return to a normal or an even safer situation following an emergency. Recovery includes getting financial assistance to help pay for the repairs. Recovery activities take place after an emergency.

Local governments make plans and provide resources to protect their citizens from the hazards that threaten their communities. This is done through mitigation activities, preparedness plans, response to emergencies, and recovery operations. Wherever you live within the United States, a county or municipal agency has been designated as your local emergency management agency. The local government level is the most important at which to develop emergency management plans because local governments serve as the link between you and the State and Federal agencies in the emergency management network[3].

Local law will specify a chain of command in emergencies. It will spell out who reports to whom. The chief executive officer or jurisdiction manager is charged with creating effective emergency services. The State emergency management office is responsible for protecting communities and citizens within the State. The State office carries out statewide emergency management activities, helps coordinate emergency management activities involving more than one community, or assists individual communities when they need help. If any community lacks the resources needed to protect itself or to recover from a disaster, the State may help with money, personnel, or other resources.

Financial assistance is available on a supplemental basis through an application process. The Governor reviews the local government's application, studies the damage estimates and, if appropriate, declares the area a State disaster. This official declaration makes State resources available. However, if damages are so extensive that the combined local and State resources are not sufficient, the Governor applies to the President for Federal disaster assistance. If the need for Federal assistance funds is justified, the President issues a major disaster declaration and Federal resources are made available. This system ensures that the State and Federal limited resources are used wisely and fairly, and the needs of disaster victims are met.

To sum up all given facts above, it should be noted that state emergency management offices often have various names and procedures for operating. Titles commonly used include Emergency Management, Civil Defense, Civil Preparedness, and Disaster Services. In this text,

the term emergency management is used to refer to these State offices. The State is the pivotal point between policy guidance and resources available at the Federal level and the implementation of comprehensive emergency management programs at the local level.

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